

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

D5.3 A suite of resources to support the growth of IPSP sustainability

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Funded by
the European Union

DISCLAIMER

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon -WIDERA-2021-ERA-01 research and innovation programme.

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Consortium overview

AMU	UNIVERSITÉ D'AIX MARSEILLE	FR
PVM	PROTISVALOR MEDITERRANEE SAS	FR
OPERAS	OPEN SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA FOR THE HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES	BE
CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	FR
EIFL	STICHTING EIFL.NET	NL
FECYT	FUNDACIÓN ESPAÑOLA PARA LA CIENCIA Y LA TECNOLOGIA, F.S.P., FECYT	ES
TSV	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAIN VALTUUSKUNNASTA	FI
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
UB	UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA	ES
UniZD	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZADRU	HR
FFZG	SVEUČILIŠTE U ZAGREBU FILOZOFSKI FAKULTET	HR
Science Europe	SCIENCE EUROPE	BE
EUA	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY ASSOCIATION	BE
OASPA	STICHTING OPEN ACCESS SCHOLARLY PUBLISHERS ASSOCIATION	NL
UiT	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	NO

CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
UGOE	GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT GÖTTINGEN STIFTUNG ÖFFENTLICHEN RECHTS	DE
SPE	STICHTING SPARC EUROPE	NL
UU	UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL
EKT	ETHNIKO KENTRO TEKMIRIOSIS KAI ILEKTRONIKOU PERIECHOMENOU	EL
IBL PAN	INSTYTUT BADAN LITERACKICH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	PL
ESF	FONDATION EUROPÉENNE DE LA SCIENCE	FR
JISC	JISC LBG	UK
DOAJ	INFRASTRUCTURE SERVICES FOR OPEN ACCESS C I C	UK

Document overview

Project Acronym:	DIAMAS
Project Name:	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
Project No:	101058007
Start Date:	01/09/2022
End Date:	31/08/2025

[D5.3 Tool Suite of resources]

Contributing WP	WP5
WP Leader:	SPARC Europe
Deliverable identifier:	D5.3 Toolsuite
Contractual Delivery Date: 02/2020	Actual Delivery Date: 02/2025
Nature: Other	Version: 1.0 Final
Dissemination level	PU

Version history

Version	Created/Modified	Comments
0.0	Authors	First draft (documentation and website)
0.1	Authors	Final draft for review
0.2	Reviewers	Review copy with comment
1.0	Authors	Final draft

Acronyms

AEUP	Association of European University Presses
CAP	Common Access Point

CoNOSC	Council for National Open Science Coordination
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOAS	Diamond Open Access Standard
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EQSIP	Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing
ERA	European Research Area
FSDs	Funders, Sponsors and Donors
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	International Advisory Board
IPSP	Institutional Publisher and Service Provider
IPTP	Institutional Publisher and Technical Providers
OA	Open Access
OAPEN	Open Access Publishing in European Networks

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OIPA	Open Institutional Publishing Association
OPERAS	European Research Infrastructure for the development of open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities
OS	Open Science
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
UKSG	United Kingdom Serials Group
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report outlines the design and development of the toolsuite of sustainability resources for Institutional Publisher Service Providers (IPSPs), a deliverable of the DIAMAS Project, Work Package (WP) 5: Exploring and supporting the sustainability of institutional publishing (Task 5.5).

It includes a description of the process that led to the writing and publication of the resources, including their review and integration with the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH). It also refers to the dissemination of the toolsuite, engagement activities around the resources and provides considerations about future sustainability and development.

We define the toolsuite of sustainability resources as a set of tools and resources, such as case studies, templates, reports and recommended readings that IPSPs and funders, sponsors and donors (FSDs) can use to both advocate for, and to support the practical implementation of, Diamond Open Access (OA).

The toolsuite of sustainability resources launched in January 2025 and can be accessed at <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/toolsuite-sustainability>.

The resources are grouped into four sections: Advocacy Resources; Tools; Research; the evidence base; and Further reading. All the resources have been internally reviewed by project partners before being sent for external review and integrated within the EDCH. The design and development of the EDCH were assigned to Pontemedia following the evaluation of their submitted proposal.

The resources are also available to download from Zenodo. Individual DOIs can be found in Section 1.0 and additional information in Annex 1. Further additions are planned before the end of the DIAMAS Project in month 36 (August 2025). These include resources to support collaboration practices for IPSPs in Europe in month 31 (March 2025).

1.0 Introduction

This report outlines the design and development of the toolsuite of sustainability resources for IPSPs, a deliverable of the DIAMAS Project, WP5: Exploring and supporting the sustainability of institutional publishing (Task 5.5). WP5 was led by SPARC Europe.

The task began in month 20 (April 2024) of the DIAMAS Project, with the deliverable deadline in month 30 (February 2025). This deliverable comprises the design and development of a collection of ten new resources to support key stakeholder groups, in particular, IPSPs, in assessing to what extent they are financially sustainable, and providing them with tools and intelligence to help them become more so in the future, as well as seeing how to better target FSDs who may commit to investing in them.

This sustainability resource collection was integrated into the Resources & Guidelines area of the EDCH, which was publicly launched in Madrid (14–15 January 2025). This collection can be accessed at <https://toolsuite.diamas.org/toolsuite-sustainability>.

More related resources will be added to the collection as they come online. For example, resources that are outcomes of DIAMAS Task 5.2 (Identify areas of potential collaboration) will be launched in month 31 (March 2025). Although T5.2 does not have its own dedicated deliverable, the output of all the information gathering activity (via national and regional focus groups and desk-based research) will detail collaboration practices for IPSPs in Europe. This includes the identification of existing practices as well as obstacles and how to overcome them, all of which will be invaluable to IPSPs and FSDs. In addition, we have invited the wider community to propose existing useful resources that could be added to the toolsuite of sustainability resources, and we hope to grow the collection organically over time.

Further information about the ten new resources we created is available as part of this report (see Annex 1). The individual files can also be downloaded from the DIAMAS community on Zenodo:

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- Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access <https://zenodo.org/records/14727743>
- The centrality of the workforce for Diamond OA: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work <https://zenodo.org/records/14626445>
- Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access <https://zenodo.org/records/14904444>
- How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide <https://zenodo.org/records/14898558>
- Nonprofit Business Model Canvas <https://zenodo.org/records/14621236>
- Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers <https://zenodo.org/records/14621767>
- Research funders committing to Diamond OA: A DIAMAS case study report <https://zenodo.org/records/14626659>
- Diamond Open Access sustainability check statements <https://zenodo.org/records/13833718>
- Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe <https://zenodo.org/records/10907086>
- National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe <https://zenodo.org/records/11383941>

Some of these resources will have to be updated as more EDCH services come online, for example, some signpost to the Registry Institutional Publisher and Technical Providers (IPTPs) and Forum, virtual spaces dedicated to fostering collaboration and networking among Diamond Open Access Community Members.

This report describes the processes behind the creation of the toolsuite of sustainability resources. It covers the goals and objectives, methodology, writing and review processes, touching upon technical aspects such as the development of, and integration with, the EDCH. It also includes a plan for subsequent dissemination and engagement activity to showcase the toolsuite more widely, and outlines how the toolsuite will be managed and developed during the remainder of the DIAMAS Project, as well as following project conclusion.

2.0 Description of the Toolsuite

2.1 Goals and Objectives

The development of the toolsuite of sustainability resources began in month 20 (April 2024) as a deliverable of WP5 (Exploring and supporting the sustainability of institutional publishing). This collection of resources, developed under Jisc's leadership, is one of the main deliverables of WP5, and is the culmination of extensive fact finding, research and speaking to our community members.

To meet the terms and conditions of the Grant Agreement (GA), the toolsuite of sustainability resources must:

1. Consist of different types of resources that meet the needs of the two main stakeholder groups (IPSPs and FSDs) and that can be utilised to support their financial sustainability.
2. Specifically delve into the revenue models classed as Diamond OA.
3. Be developed and refined using feedback from the full range of stakeholders.
4. Integrate with other DIAMAS outputs (D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite and Guidelines) as part of the planned Common Access Point (CAP).

The toolsuite creates and presents new materials and builds on existing resources and earlier outputs from WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP7 of the DIAMAS Project, including D5.1 (Brun, V., 2024) and D5.2 (Taşkın, Z., 2024). It contains ten new resources, from advocacy aids to concrete tools that guide, instruct and inspire, to evidence-based research which are part of the new EDCH.

We carried out extensive stakeholder engagement activity and analysis to garner the needs of, and establish gaps and challenges for certain stakeholder groups, such as IPSPs and FSDs, around the financial sustainability of supporting Diamond OA. It was decided to deliver a collection of resources in month 30 (February 2025), as promised in the GA, but then continue to produce resources and updates as necessary, utilising the knowledge of the wider EDCH community.

2.2 Methodology

Desk-based research established numerous existing outputs (both internal and external to DIAMAS) around the financial sustainability of Diamond OA (such as past project reports, data sets, focus groups, interviews and surveys) that would be of interest to these IPSPs and FSDs.

The collaboration platform Miro (<https://miro.com/>) was used to share ideas in a more visual manner and highlight both commonalities between stakeholders and synergies between other areas of the CAP e.g. the IPTP registry. The CAP is being developed as a federated infrastructure that integrates interoperable components and provides guidance and tools to support the sustainability of Diamond OA institutional publishing. It also fosters the creation of a community of practice among Diamond OA publishers, service providers, and technology providers in Europe.

Keeping the stakeholder point of view at the forefront, and thinking about what IPSPs and FSDs need to know about the financial sustainability of Diamond OA, we challenged ourselves to drill down, distill and develop the information in a more user friendly, manageable way. Whilst using existing data to drive the development and creation of

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new resources, it was also an opportunity to signpost readers to other resources on similar topics, such as journal articles. Not only did these resources complement our collection of brand new content, from a user perspective, pulling together and re-packaging all relevant resources into one single-point-of-truth is preferable to multiple sources of information.

Before the writing process could begin, and the team could formalise their ideas around how to display information in a more user friendly way, e.g. checklists, one-pagers of recommendations, infographics, templates to help with advocacy and practical implementation, into concrete resources, the following was discussed and determined:

1. What is the goal of the toolsuite?
2. Who is it for?
3. Who is going to benefit?
4. What problem is it going to solve?
5. What things do we want to create, and for whom?

DIAMAS and its sister project, CRAFT-OA (<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>), held regular events which were opportunities to spot gaps, verify ideas, solicit further feedback and establish D5.3 was moving forward correctly meeting the needs, in particular, of IPSPs and FSDs.

These included the three events in the 'DIAMAS Conversation series for libraries: Advancing Diamond OA in Europe' (Advancing Diamond OA in Europe; Standards and Tools to Elevate Diamond OA Publishing; Toolsuite & Guidelines for OA publishing), as well as two other DIAMAS webinars (Strength through collaboration in Diamond OA publishing; Seeking to make the life of the learned society publisher easier), as well as DIAMAS focus groups in different languages.

Furthermore, a presentation at the Council for National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC) meeting, where national Open Science (OS) policymakers discussed funding Diamond OA, enabled outreach to FSDs on the topic.

2.3 Writing Process

Following the extensive desk-based research into existing resources that could be repackaged into the sustainability toolsuite, and team discussions as to what new resources were needed, and for whom, the writing process began with the assignment of lead authors for each resource.

Although a template was initially provided for lead authors to use (based on the Articles in OAPEN's OA Books Toolkit), it became evident that to meet the demands of creating a variety of resources, as per the GA, the content would not fit into a 'one size fits all' document. The lead authors worked from blank documents, which were formatted following the external review process (see Sections 2.4 and 2.5).

As aforementioned, draft resources were continually reviewed as writing progressed. Partners were encouraged to comment on the resources as they developed, adding their expertise for a more holistic view. This preliminary internal review process meant that when the first drafts were circulated outside WP5, e.g. to other WP leaders, project partners, and the project coordinator, there were limited comments and suggestions to respond to and incorporate.

Thanks to this workflow, the first five resources were ready ahead of schedule. This was serendipitous as the project coordinator requested that the sustainability toolsuite be live for the EDCH launch event in Madrid on 15 January 2025, six weeks ahead of the deliverable deadline.

Resources were then collated before being forwarded to members of the International Advisory Board (IAB) for feedback (see Section 2.4 for further information about this process). After external peer review, the lead authors made the suggested edits, and the resources were copy-edited and formatted using a specific sub output template designed by WP7, thus ensuring consistency in font and style (see Section 2.5 for more information about project branding). The resources were then locked down so no further editing could take place and to prevent any discrepancies with the published versions and the final versions hosted on Google drive.

The resources were then published to the DIAMAS community on Zenodo; the DOIs were then sent to Pontemedia (see Section 2.6.1) to be uploaded to the EDCH along with a short description.

2.3.1 Glossary and Keywords

A full glossary of terms and a list of keywords in D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite and Guidelines (launched October 2024) were incorporated into the EDCH. Both are essential to maximise use of all the resources within the EDCH, allowing users to cross-check, expand their knowledge and navigate smoothly between different areas.

The first iteration of the Glossary was created as part of the preparation for the WP2 Landscape survey (Bargheer et al., 2023), and the full process by which D4.2 built upon it

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is described in D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite and Guidelines (Armengou, 2024). D5.3 lead authors were tasked with looking through the existing Glossary on the EDCH and adding to it if needed. These additional terms, which can be found in Annex 2, will be translated into the same set of languages (Croatian, Portuguese and Spanish) as the translation of both the DOAS guidelines and the articles.

Similarly, the EDCH also contains a list of common Keywords found across all the resources. These are used to tag resources, allowing users to move seamlessly between related items. Although the sustainability resources are not hosted directly on the EDCH (instead they are hosted on other platforms such as Zenodo), the EDCH is currently in beta and it is possible the structure of the sustainability resources landing page will change in the future and Keywords will be incorporated. Therefore, D5.3 lead authors were also tasked with adding to the Keywords list. These additional words can be found in Annex 3. They are also duplicated in the Zenodo metadata records to enhance discoverability.

2.4 Review Process

The review of the deliverables (Julian, A. & James, J., 2024) states that two reviewers are chosen per deliverable on the basis of the following criteria:

- One of the reviewers is external to the team in charge of the writing of the report. As a minimum, one reviewer will be selected for each deliverable, two if possible;
- The second reviewer is the co-coordinator.

The weekly WP leader meetings and fortnightly WP5 meetings represented additional opportunities to discuss the progress on deliverables and share early versions of content for informal review. External reviewers were selected from the IAB and the final editor/reviewer was one of the co-coordinators, Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S).

As discussed above, the internal review process of the resources happened organically with WP5 members providing feedback as writing progressed. Lead authors also garnered feedback from their individual networks, organisations and institutions outside of DIAMAS, thus creating another helpful layer of evaluation.

Once the lead authors had responded to all feedback and incorporated suggestions into the copy, the resources were reviewed by Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe), WP5 leader, and DIAMAS co-coordinator Johan Rooryck (cOAlition S) before being elevated to external reviewers.

The resources were also reviewed externally. Suitable members of the IAB were identified and asked to review both the content of the resources and the deliverable report. Due to the time pressures created by the imminent launch of the EDCH, the five resources that were ready for review first were collectively passed to the following reviewers in December 2024, with the understanding that at least two more resources, plus the deliverable report, would follow at a later date.

The external reviewers selected were:

- Jessica Dallaire-Clark (Senior Coordinator, Open Access Development, Érudit)
- Sharla Lair, Senior Strategist of Open Access and Scholarly Communication Initiatives, Lyrisis
- Jeroen Sondervan, Programme Leader Open Scholarly Communication, Open Science NL

They were requested to provide feedback on the resources, including any suggested amendments, identification of missing information, and recommendations for supporting references and additional reading. The lead authors of each resource then reviewed the comments and revised content as necessary.

2.5 Formatting and Design

The sustainability resources were all formatted according to the Website, Communication Kit, and Social Media Presence documents provided by DIAMAS (Blake, 2023). While D4.2 had followed a template (Armengou et al., 2024) for their Toolsuite Articles and Guidelines, due to the different types of resources created as part of D5.3, this was not suitable (see Section 2.2). To ensure consistency with the overall DIAMAS brand identity, in collaboration with WP7, a specific sub output template was designed specifically to match the needs of the sustainability toolsuite resources.

Due to the launch of the EDCH, and a shorter deadline than originally expected, the decision was made to host the sustainability resources within the DIAMAS community on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/diamasproject/>). The Zenodo URL and a short description of each resource was then added to the Sustainability Resources section on the EDCH. A benefit of using Zenodo is that it helps monitor and track impact, such as usage and downloads, and also ensures that users can easily access the most recent version of the resource.

Based on the project coordinator's feedback following the launch of the EDCH, the sustainability toolsuite content was reorganised in month 30 (February 2025) under the following headings to enhance navigation and increase user-friendliness:

- **Advocacy Resources** - new resources designed to support individuals in upwards conversations around the importance of supporting Diamond OA. They

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offer guidance on how to effectively communicate with IPSPs and FSDs to influence change

- **Tools** - a collection of functional new resources to implement Diamond OA and an array of practical new assets to employ when putting Diamond OA into practice
- **Research, the evidence base** - DIAMAS reports containing data and desk-based research from across the European Research Area (ERA) which served as inspiration for, and underpin, the new resources created
- **Further reading** - relevant reading from across the sector. This is the area we hope to develop further with the support of the EDCH.

2.6 Technical Development

This section details the technical framework of the online component of the resource toolsuite, highlighting key aspects of its development and deployment.

2.6.1 Design, Hosting and Infrastructure

The design and development of the EDCH was assigned to Pontemedia (2020) following the evaluation of their submitted proposal by an appointed committee of project partners, based on predefined selection criteria. Pontemedia is an IT company specialised in the development of CMS-based online installations.

They responded to a public call for the technical implementation of the D4.3 toolsuite and other components of the EDCH (March 2024). Content for the EDCH was initially hosted on a Pontemedia staging server for development and testing purposes, while interoperability workflows between the toolsuite and other components of the EDCH were established.

2.6.2 Content Structure

The sustainability toolsuite sits in the Resources & Guidelines section of the EDCH, an area containing a variety of tools and resources to support publishers who already are, or who are considering moving towards Diamond OA publishing. The webpage content is organised into the following main sections, with the sustainability resources grouped under four headings for easy navigation by readers and usability purposes (see Section 2.5):

- Diamond OA
 - What is Diamond OA
 - Introduction to DOAS
- Tools and resources
 - Toolsuite Articles
 - Guidelines

- **Sustainability Resources**
 - **Advocacy Resources**
 - **Tools**
 - **Research, the evidence base**
 - **Further reading**
- Self-assessment tools
- FAQs
- Glossary
- Useful links
- **About the Tool Suite**
 - How to Browse the Tool Suite
 - Acknowledgements
 - Help and Feedback

2.6.3 Visual Style Guide

The website's visual style, including fonts, weights, logo, and colours, is based on the Website, Communication Kit, and Social Media Presence documents provided by DIAMAS (Blake, 2023). This ensures consistency with the overall DIAMAS brand identity.

2.6.4 Accessibility

The sustainability toolsuite was developed with accessibility in mind, adhering to the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 AA standards (W3C, 2008). This ensures that the website is usable and accessible to people with a wide range of disabilities.

2.6.5 Security

The EDCH website will be served over HTTPS using Let's Encrypt certificates for secure communication in the production environment. Regular security updates will be applied to the server, Drupal core, and contributed modules to mitigate potential vulnerabilities. Appropriate user roles and permissions are implemented within Drupal to restrict access to sensitive areas and functionalities.

2.7 Feedback and Revision

Suggestions for the Further reading section are particularly welcomed as the Diamond OA publishing space develops. This will ensure that the relevancy and currency of resources are maintained and that there is involvement from the Diamond OA community. Updated versions of the newly created resources will also need to be added as new areas of the EDCH come online, for example, the IPTP.

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All feedback on the toolsuite and suggestions for revisions and additions can be sent via email to toolsuite@diamas.org. As responsibility for the longer term management of the sustainability resource section is still to be confirmed, it is advisable to have a generic contact point rather than a named individual in case of personnel changes at project partners.

3.0 Outreach Activities and Further Developments

This section details the engagement activity throughout the duration of D5.3, including the EDCH launch, and shares plans for the wider dissemination and development of the toolsuite of sustainability resources following the deliverable deadline.

3.1 Engagement

Engagement with, and dissemination of, the toolsuite of sustainability resources is vital to ensure continued usage and relevancy. As mentioned earlier in the report, extensive stakeholder engagement activity was undertaken earlier in the DIAMAS project, the outcomes of which culminated in other project outputs of WP5, including D5.1 and D5.2.

This previous stakeholder activity provided a richness and depth of knowledge of the institutional publishing landscape across Europe, and as such, proved invaluable when developing our resources. For example, the Institutional Publishing Landscape Report (Armengou, 2023) is built on 685 survey responses from IPSPs across the ERA, and the D5.1 IPSP Sustainability Research Report (Brun, V., 2024) included two quantitative surveys (the DIAMAS survey and a follow-up survey focusing on funding practices), six focus groups with national-based IPSPs, and fifteen interviews with a range of diverse institutional publishing representatives.

Engagement with key stakeholder groups throughout the writing process allowed us to refine our resources as they developed. We utilised the regular events held by DIAMAS and its sister project, CRAFT-OA, to interact with the stakeholder groups our resources were aimed at, e.g. IPSPs and FSDs. These included the 'DIAMAS Conversation series for libraries: Advancing Diamond OA in Europe', events that brought together learned societies, libraries, publishers and other interested parties, a presentation at the CoNOSC meeting where national OS policymakers discussed funding Diamond OA, focus groups in different languages on the topic and workshops around the Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) and DOAS as well as at a workshop at the Munin Conference in 2024. These opportunities shared draft resources, spotted gaps, verified ideas, solicited further feedback and established D5.3 was moving forward correctly meeting the needs, in particular, of IPSPs and FSDs. In addition, they also met

the promise in the GA to discuss findings and options with FSDs, Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), learned societies and the IPSP network of WP4.

3.2 Outreach

3.2.1 Social Media

Social media and other online platforms have so far played a huge part in disseminating and amplifying the toolsuite of sustainability resources to a wider audience.

The DIAMAS social media strategy was established by Blake et al. (2023) and alongside the DIAMAS website (<https://diamasproject.eu/>), we utilised the DIAMAS profiles on X (Twitter) and LinkedIn. These were managed by project partner LIBER as part of WP7.

- X (Twitter): <https://x.com/DiamasProject>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/diamas-project/>

The launch of the toolsuite of sustainability resources, as part of the EDCH in January 2025, was accompanied by social media campaigns on X (Twitter) and LinkedIn with the expectation that project partners would amplify the content and re-share with national networks, as well as adapt for other platforms, such as Bluesky, Facebook, Threads and Mastodon. This was managed by SPARC Europe.

A series of linked posts was created, highlighting each resource individually accompanied by a brief description and a link to the resource in Zenodo. Posts were accompanied by eye-catching social media cards to maximise impact. These will be updated and the campaign re-run following the addition of new resources in February and March and then repeated to continue engaging with the community and inviting further involvement.

Although DIAMAS has met its social media KPIs, and considering the ongoing discussions about the value and ethics of X (Twitter) as a platform, the decision was made by WP7 to continue using it as a dissemination tool until project conclusion. However, the updated thread of social media posts designed for X (Twitter) will be duplicated on Bluesky by WP5 lead, SPARC Europe.

3.2.2 Email Marketing

Email marketing was strategically used to disseminate the toolsuite of sustainability resources more widely. Project partners were contacted and asked to share D5.3 with national networks and relevant organisations e.g. Open Institutional Publishing Association (OIPA), via mailing lists, e-newsletters and listserv. Suggested copy was created and shared to ensure accuracy and consistency of information. This tactic was successful in the United Kingdom with multiple organisations from the scholarly

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communications and publishing sectors sharing the resources via their e-newsletters, for example, the British Library and the United Kingdom Serials Group (UKSG), thus reaching a wider and more varied audience. As with the updated social media campaigns, email communication with project partners will be repeated following the deliverable deadline.

3.3 Outreach

In order to disseminate the toolsuite of sustainability resources more widely, there are plans progressing to showcase D5.3 at multiple events for the remainder of the DIAMAS Project. Alongside DIAMAS events such as the 'Conversation with Libraries' series, other webinars and the end of project conference (2-3 June 2025, Brussels, Belgium), we are exploring external opportunities for WP5 members to present at conferences.

WP5 lead SPARC Europe will give a keynote at the 2025 4th Association of European University Presses (AEUP) Conference "Sustaining the Flow: Keeping the Pages Turning in Scholarly Publishing" (22-23 May, Vienna, Austria), and we will submit a further proposal to share the toolsuite of sustainability resources more widely in another format, either a presentation, a vignette or a poster.

We have suggested the toolsuite as a topic to be discussed at the Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing (18-20 November 2025, Tromsø, Norway) which is also streamed worldwide.

Regional events offer the opportunity for face-to-face multilingual interactions with national and regional audiences. We will be running a workshop, "Implementing Sustainability Tools for Diamond OA", for the Open-Access-Tage (19-20 March 2025, Bern, Switzerland). The workshop will focus on the implementability of the Sustainability Toolsuite and thereby simultaneously work as a dissemination, community engagement and feedback measure for a large German-speaking audience.

As part of our outreach and engagement strategy going forward, we will explore other avenues and opportunities with the EDCH as they come online, for example, the Diamond OA Community Network via the IPTP Registry and the Forum, and the Task Forces responsible for the development of the EDCH. Many of the project partners involved with both DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA are also involved in EDCH Task Forces, thus allowing for continuity and understanding.

3.4 Further Developments

As part of WP5, a selection of resources to support collaboration practices for IPSPs in Europe will also be added to the sustainability toolsuite in month 31 (March 2025). Plans

are already underway to integrate these within the EDCH Resources & Guidelines section, as described earlier in this report.

Another DIAMAS deliverable, D4.4 IPSP training materials, is also due in month 31 (March 2025). As stated above, in addition to creating new resources, this deliverable also repurposes content from the toolsuite articles and guidelines into a set of learning resources; these will be added to the Resources & Guidelines area on the EDCH.

Subsequent to the above, the EDCH Glossary and Keywords will be updated as appropriate.

Although not a requirement of the GA for D5.3, if there is a demand, we would like to investigate the possibility of translating the sustainability resources into the same set of languages (Croatian, Portuguese and Spanish) as the translation of both the DOAS guidelines and the articles. This would be done following the same workflow as D4.2 e.g., using the pilot translation service Mondaecus, an online platform developed by the University of Coimbra (Da Silva Ferreira & Silva, 2023; Silva, 2024; University of Coimbra, n.d.). Community support (and resource) for this could be gauged via the EDCH Forum (<https://forum.diamas.org/>) as well as the wider European Diamond OA community.

By offering resources in multiple languages, DIAMAS ensures that a broader audience can access and benefit from its tools and guidance (Ševkušić, M., 2025). However, discussions around further translations are still in their infancy and form part of the wider dialogue on how the toolsuite will progress as part of the EDCH, in particular, how the community will be involved in its subsequent use and development.

Additionally, there are opportunities for members of the Diamond OA Forum and the wider European Diamond OA community to be involved in suggesting revisions, new content and providing general feedback. These are also discussed in Sections 2.7 and 4.2.

4.0 Sustainability

There are a number of considerations that need to be taken into account regarding the longevity of the toolsuite of sustainability resources; technical maintenance of the web pages and relevancy of the content.

4.1 Technical Maintenance

As an open-source platform, Drupal offers benefits that ensure the technical sustainability of the online toolsuite. It is supported by an active community of developers and allows customisations using built-in modules or plugins, whereas the platform's functionalities are regularly updated and upgraded, ensuring its relevance to current technical, security, and interoperability standards. Moreover, the selection of an

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open-source platform reduces reliance on third-party solutions or proprietary software that may become obsolete or unsupported as well as the dependency on IT providers who maintain proprietary platforms. Throughout the project's duration, Pontemedia will undertake the following tasks as part of their assignments:

- Regular security audits of the platform's configurations to identify potential vulnerabilities.
- Regular reviews for compliance with accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG).
- Regular software updates to integrate new features and functionalities.
- Monitoring of the platform's performance and technical support in case of malfunctions.

The long-term technical sustainability of the online toolsuite will be ensured through the integration of the Drupal platform into the EDCH, which is being developed as a federated infrastructure of interoperable components. Maintenance and upgrades will be coordinated by a dedicated Task Force and supported by structural funds and technical experts.

4.2 Resource Maintenance

The DIAMAS Project comes to an end in month 36 (August 2025) when responsibility for the toolsuite of sustainability resources will transfer to the EDCH Community Task Force (<https://diamas.org/task-forces>), which will coordinate further updates. Until that date, WP5 has committed to keeping all new resources updated, for example, adding links to the IPTP Registry into "Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond OA publishers" when it comes online. Project partners with responsibility for outputs will keep them up-to-date and accessible, for example, checking that links are still live.

All feedback on the toolsuite, alongside suggestions for revisions and additions, can be sent via email to toolsuite@diamas.org. We will also invite feedback from users of the resources at DIAMAS webinars and conference presentations.

Once online, it is perceived that the members of the Diamond Open Access Forum will play a crucial role in sustaining, developing and exploiting the EDCH, including the maintenance and development of all sections. Moderators will be encouraged to initiate conversations around individual resources, for example, how they are being used and what has been the most useful. These will feed into subsequent updates, for example, users of 'Consider your options: exploring the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access' will be invited to add their examples to the different funding and revenue stream options listed in the resource.

5.0 Conclusion

The full tool suite of sustainability resources is available online and has been integrated with the D4.2 IPSP Toolsuite and Guidelines as part of the Resources & Guidelines section of the EDCH, which launched in January 2025.

The toolsuite of sustainability resources brings together a collection of resources for IPSPs and FSDs to support the sustainability of institutional publishing. These resources are a mixture of tools, templates, case studies, and reports that IPSPs and FSDs can utilise in the future to both advocate for and to support the practical implementation of Diamond OA. The collection also acts as a signpost to further reading on this topic.

Not only do these resources meet a known need for support around financial sustainability from multiple stakeholder groups (as established by desk-based research and earlier outreach and engagement activities), they specifically target and assist IPSPs and FSDs. They are supported through a variety of resources, such as one pagers, templates, case studies and longer reports, which can be used in different contexts and situations.

As such, we have delivered on the GA for the intended audience, namely IPSPs and FSDs.

We have created a multiplicity of resources to suit different stakeholders and their needs, all built on the evidence garnered throughout the project, and building on some of our key outputs such as the D5.1 IPSP Sustainability Research Report (Brun et al., 2024).

Throughout the writing process, we drew on what we were learning from IPSPs, FSDs, libraries, learned societies and other interested parties attending DIAMAS engagement activities, such as webinars and focus groups. What we heard and learnt during these events fed into the design and development of the new resources, which were further refined using feedback from the full range of stakeholders. All resources undertook a rigorous internal and external review process with sector specialists.

Additional parts will be added to the collection in the remaining months of the project as they come online. A selection of resources to support collaboration practices for IPSPs in Europe will be integrated into the sustainability toolsuite in month 31 (March 2025), existing resources will be updated to signpost to new sections of the EDCH, and plans are underway for additional reading and useful resources to be suggested by the Diamond OA community.

The sustainability toolsuite is an integral part of the EDCH, and the longer-term management and update of the platform will be essential to support the IPSP and FSD communities in building a more financially sustainable Diamond OA ecosystem.

6.0 References

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Annex 1: List of Toolsuite Resources

1.1 Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access

These [talking points](#) list a range of reasons for institutions, funders, donors and sponsors to invest in Diamond Open Access publishing.

1.2 The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work

This [short article](#) explains how significant the workforce is to sustaining Diamond Open Access publishing and what challenges these workers face.

1.3 Consider your options: explore the different funding or revenue streams for Diamond Open Access

[D5.3 Tool Suite of resources]

This [list](#) provides an overview of different funding mechanisms that Diamond Open Access publishers and service providers can use to acquire financial or other resources needed for their OA diamond operations or development.

1.4 How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide

[Guidance](#) on how to make the case for supporting your Diamond Open Access publication, project, service or infrastructure.

1.5 Nonprofit Business Model Canvas

This [guide](#) explains the use of the Nonprofit Business Model Canvas as a strategic management tool and provides a planning template.

1.6 Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers

This [guide](#) is designed to help Diamond Open Access publishers manage their expenses and save resources. It walks them through the typical costs involved in running a Diamond Open Access publishing project, with questions that encourage them to think about their current practices and explore ways to optimise costs.

1.7 Diamond Open Access sustainability check

This online tool (<https://diamas.fecyt.es/>) is for Diamond Open Access publishers and Diamond Open Access service providers to gain insights into their financial health to help plan for a more sustainable future. Note the tool consists of two parallel instances: DOAS and the Sustainability Check that can be completed sequentially, if desired. The list of statements from the Diamond OA Sustainability Check tool are available in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/13833718>) and can be used in parallel to, or instead of, the digital Diamond OA Sustainability Check tool.

1.8 Research funders committing to Diamond Open Access: A DIAMAS case study report

This [report](#) provides a set of insights into why and how research funders are trying to support Diamond Open Access publishing. It provides case studies examining different funders and their motivations and funding mechanisms, and what this means for their work.

1.9 Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe

Available as both a [full report](#) and a [brief summary of key findings](#), this research investigates what financial sustainability means for institutional publishing in Europe and the workforce involved in it. The analysis draws on four types of data: a literature review of economic and financial aspects of institutional publishing, two quantitative surveys (the DIAMAS survey and a follow-up survey focusing on funding practices), six focus groups with national-based Institutional Publishers and Service Providers, and fifteen interviews with a range of diverse institutional publishing representatives.

1.10 National overviews on sustaining institutional publishing in Europe

As both a [full report](#) and a [factsheet](#), this deep dive into ten national contexts shows a wide variety of conditions for funding Diamond Open Access: Croatia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, United Kingdom (UK).

1.11 Literature on Diamond Open Access publications and infrastructure business models

A community collection of publications and literature on Diamond Open Access publishing and infrastructure business models.

https://www.zotero.org/groups/5034288/literature_on_diamond_open_access_publications_and_infrastructure_business_models/library

1.12 Beyond 'no fee': why Diamond Open Access is much more than a business model

This chapter seeks to explore the various dimensions of Diamond Open Access from multiple perspectives. By attempting to move beyond the simplistic and technical definition of 'no-fee' Open Access, the authors aim to uncover the complex dynamics that underpin knowledge production, as well as the roles that publishers, scholars, institutions, and academic communities play within these processes.

[D5.3 Tool Suite of resources]

Gatti, R., Mounier, P., & Rooryck, J. (2024). Beyond 'no fee': why Diamond Open Access is much more than a business model (Preprint). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14440034>

1.13 How to flip your journal: A guide to more equitable publishing with Diamond Open Access

This guide has been written for all journal editors (in the Netherlands and beyond) who find themselves uncomfortable with the hold of commercial publishers over their journals and would like to transition their journal to a Diamond Open Access publication model. It provides an overview of which steps to take while considering the flip to Diamond Open Access, which routes are possible (subscribe to open, university presses, publishing platforms and do-it-yourself publishing) and which are the costs and possibility of funding the journal under the new model.

Constantin, M., de Leeuwe, J., van Rijn, S., Saive, M., Tarchi, A., & de Vries, H. (2025). How to flip your journal: A guide to more equitable publishing with Diamond Open Access. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652446>

Annex 2: Glossary

Article landing page

Article landing page is a dedicated webpage for a specific journal article. It is the primary access point where readers can find detailed information about the article, such as metadata, abstracts, and links to the full text.

HTML meta tags

HTML meta tags are elements in the HTML code, namely the head section of a webpage, that provide structured metadata about the page, such as author information, title, keywords, description, etc. These tags are not directly visible on the page. They help search engines and browsers capture and process the content, improving the page's visibility and search ranking.

Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS)

Journal Article Tag Suite (JATS) is an XML format designed to describe scholarly publications. It provides XML elements and attributes for describing both the textual and graphical content of publications.

Journal management system

Journal management system is a software platform designed to support the editorial and production workflows in scholarly journals. It provides tools and functionalities for managing the publishing process, from submission to publication.

National Research and Education Network (NREN)

A specialised internet service provider supporting the needs of the research and education communities within a country. NRENs are usually funded by governments or university consortia. They also provide secure connections, advanced digital tools and dedicated channels for individual research projects. Reference/derivation:

<https://geant.org/>

Software-as-a-Service (SaaS)

Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) is a software delivery model where applications are hosted and maintained by a provider and made accessible to users via a web browser. This model eliminates the need for managing infrastructure, updates, or hardware on the user side and can involve subscriptions for using the service. In the context of scholarly publishing, SaaS refers to cloud-based publishing platforms provided by non-profit or commercial providers, allowing publishers to manage the entire publishing workflow without having to host software locally.

Vendor lock-in

Vendor lock-in is a situation where a customer becomes dependent on a specific vendor's products, services, or technologies because it is difficult and/or expensive to switch to another provider. Such a situation can arise due to high switching costs, proprietary formats, or incompatible systems that limit interoperability. In the context of scholarly publishing software and services, vendor lock-in may happen if:

- The platform uses proprietary data formats that are incompatible with other platforms
- Migration to a different platform would require significant time, effort, technical expertise and funds.
- Service agreements impose high fees for data extraction.
- Support, updates, or customizations are exclusively controlled by the vendor.

Annex 3: Keywords

Term	Sustainability resource
Accessibility	Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe
Budget	Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access

[D5.3 Tool Suite of resources]

	<p>publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Business models	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Collaboration	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Costs	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Diversity	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p>
Donors	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p>

	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Efficiency	<p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p>
Equity	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p>
Expenses	<p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Financial planning	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>

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<p>Financial resources</p>	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
<p>Free and open-source software (FOSS)</p>	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
<p>Funding</p>	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p> <p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
<p>Funding models</p>	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p>

	Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe
Fundraising	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Governance	Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers
Grants	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Growth	<p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
In-kind support	<p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Inclusion	The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work

[D5.3 Tool Suite of resources]

Income management	<p>How to define your Diamond Open Access business case: a six-step guide</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Income reporting	<p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Indexing / indexation	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Infrastructures	<p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Metadata	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Metadata and file formats	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Multilingualism	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p>
Open Access (OA)	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p>
Peer review	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Persistent identifiers	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Preservation	<p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p>
Revenue streams	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p>

	Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe
Shared services	<p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Subsidies	<p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Sustainability	<p>Talking points: Making the case to fund Diamond Open Access</p> <p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p> <p>Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Nonprofit Business Model Canvas</p> <p>Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers</p> <p>Diamond Open Access sustainability check</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>
Visibility	Optimise your expenses: Guide for Diamond Open Access publishers
Voluntary support	<p>The centrality of the workforce for Diamond Open Access: Contractual, in-kind and voluntary work</p> <p>Understanding the financial sustainability of institutional publishers and service providers in Europe</p>

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